

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS I

Complex Polyploids: Origins, Genomic Composition, and Role of Introgressed Alleles

J. Luis Leal, Pascal Milesi, Eva Hodková, Qiujie Zhou, Jennifer James,
D. Magnus Eklund, Tanja Pyhäjärvi, Jarkko Salojärvi, and Martin Lascoux

DNA Isolation, Library Preparation and Sequencing: Detailed Description

For the newly collected samples (samples not included in previous studies), total DNA was extracted from birch bud and leaf tissues using a DNeasy Plant Mini Kit (Qiagen AG, Düsseldorf, Germany) following the instructions provided by the manufacturer, apart from the incubation during lysis which was extended to 2 hours. Individual libraries were generated using the SeqCap EZ HyperCapWorkflow (Roche AG, Basel, Switzerland) using custom probes designed for targeted exome capture (TEC) and sequenced on paired-end mode (150 bp) on an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 platform (Illumina, San Diego, CA). Target resequencing was based on a custom probe design covering 1,609 nuclear genes with a 3.2M bp cumulative target size and reduced sequence redundancy. The probe set was identical to the one used in TEC sequencing of the extra 64 TEC accessions included in this paper and which were part of a previous study (Milesi et al. 2023). Nucleotide sequence similarity was checked with USEARCH, v. 11.0.667 (Edgar 2010), using a greedy clustering algorithm (-cluster_fast) and a 0.95 identity threshold.

24 Results from the clustering analysis show that, of the 1609 nucleotide sequences, 1599 (99.4%)
25 are unique.

26 Eight additional birch accessions were obtained from The European Nucleotide Archive
27 (ENA, <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena>). These include Illumina whole genome sequencing (WGS)
28 libraries for *B. lenta*, *B. nana*, *B. occidentalis*, *B. pendula*, *B. platyphylla*, *B. populifolia*, and *B.*
29 *pubescens* specimens, which were part of a previous study (Salojärvi et al., 2017). Two alder
30 (*Alnus*) accessions, part of the same study, were also included as an outgroup. These accessions
31 were used in the phylogenetic and/or population structure analyses. Information about each
32 accession can be found in Supplementary Table S1 and *Supplementary Materials 2*.

33

34 Finally, TEC libraries for twenty *B. pendula* specimens, part of a previous study (Milesi
35 et al. 2023), were downloaded from the ENA database. These samples were used in the
36 population structure analysis. TEC was performed using the same probe set described above.
37 ENA accession run codes are listed in *Supplementary Materials 2*.

38

39 **Read Mapping and Variant Calling: Detailed Description**

40

41 The pipeline used for read mapping and variant calling generally followed the Broad
42 Institute best practices workflow (DePristo et al. 2011, Poplin et al. 2018). Sequenced reads were
43 soft-clipped for Illumina adapters using MarkIlluminaAdapters from the Picard suite, v. 2.10.3
44 (<https://broadinstitute.github.io/picard/>), and mapped to the *B. pendula* genome assembly, v.
45 Bpev01 (Salojärvi et al. 2017), using BWA-MEM v 0.7.17 (Li and Durbin 2009) and PCR and
46 optical duplicates were flagged using MarkDuplicates from the PICARD. Chromosomal
47 assignment of loci was performed on the basis of the *B. pendula* chromosomal map, v. 1.4c
48 (<https://genomevolution.org/CoGe/GenomeInfo.pl?gid=35080>, accessed 2023-01-26). For
49 samples sequenced using TEC, more than 94% (mean = 99.1%) of reads mapped to the *B.*

50 *pendula* genome (*Supplementary Materials 3*). For WGS birch samples, at least 83% (mean =
51 92.8%) of sequenced reads mapped to the *B. pendula* reference assembly. On average, about 52%
52 of reads associated to the two alder libraries mapped to the *B. pendula* genome.

53

54 Genotyping was performed with GATK 4.2.0.0 (McKenna et al., 2010) followed by site-
55 level hard filtering ([https://gatk.broadinstitute.org/hc/en-us/articles/360035890471-Hard-](https://gatk.broadinstitute.org/hc/en-us/articles/360035890471-Hard-filtering-germline-short-variants)
56 [filtering-germline-short-variants](https://gatk.broadinstitute.org/hc/en-us/articles/360035890471-Hard-filtering-germline-short-variants), accessed 2022-07-14) using the filtering conditions described
57 previously by Leal et al. (2023). For all birch and alder accessions, including those obtained
58 through WGS, only sites located within the 1,603 nuclear loci covered by the TEC exome probes
59 were considered (six of the targeted 1,609 loci had very low coverage and were excluded). Sites
60 located outside the targeted regions were excluded during downstream analysis. Non-variant
61 sites located within the targeted regions were also included in the output VCF file when
62 preparing the datasets used in the phylogenetic analysis, but excluded when generating the
63 datasets used in the analysis of population structure. See *Supplementary Materials 3* for further
64 details.

65

66 **Classification of Polyploid Specimens: Detailed Description**

67

68 We classified each sample according to its ploidy level (2X, 3X, or 4X) by estimating the
69 distribution of read counts at biallelic variant sites (Yoshida et al. 2013; Zohren et al. 2016). For
70 each sample, the ratio between the number of reads supporting the reference and alternate alleles
71 was computed for each biallelic heterozygous site using `CollectAllelicCounts` from the GATK
72 suite. If the sample is diploid (2X), the reference and alternate alleles are expected to have similar
73 read support levels, leading to a unimodal distribution of read frequencies centered on 0.5
74 (*Supplementary Fig. S2b*). For tetraploid samples (4X), the distribution of read counts is
75 expected to show three modes – at 0.25, 0.5, and 0.75 – while triploid samples (3X) are foreseen

76 to have two modes, at 0.33 and 0.66 (Supplementary Figs. S2a and S2c-e). The allelic frequency
77 associated to the dominant mode, as well as the kurtosis value associated to the distribution, are
78 shown for each sample in *Supplementary Materials 3*.

79

80 Tetraploid samples were further split into *B. pubescens* and 4X *B. pendula* by carrying
81 out a phylogenetic analysis of each individual using the genomic polarization framework
82 described in this paper. *B. pubescens* specimens contain genomic components of *B. nana* and *B.*
83 *humilis* origin (see pairing profiles shown in Supplementary Figure S2a), while in *B. pendula*
84 autotetraploids these are absent (Supplementary Fig. S2c). The same procedure can be used to
85 distinguish between *B. pendula* triploids and *B. pendula* × *B. pubescens* triploid hybrids
86 (Supplementary Figs. S2d and S2e). Ploidal and taxonomic classification of each of the samples
87 included in this study, based on the approach just described, is shown in *Supplementary*
88 *Materials 3*.

89

90 **Generation of Consensus Sequences and Multiple Sequence Alignments (MSA): Detailed** 91 **Description**

92

93 Consensus sequences were generated for each accession using bcftools consensus v 1.12
94 (Danecek et al. 2021) by applying single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) specific to each
95 individual to the *B. pendula* reference assembly. Heterozygotic sites were coded following the
96 IUPAC nomenclature (Cornish-Bowden 1985). Deletions and failed variants were subsequently
97 masked using maskfasta from bedtools v 2.29.2 (Quinlan and Hall 2010). As only invariant sites
98 and point mutations were used when producing each consensus sequence, consensus sequences
99 associated to different samples are aligned by default: they all have the same length and retain
100 identical start positions for each gene, and therefore require no further alignment (Leal et al.
101 2023). Separate MSAs were produced for each of the 1,603 loci included in the analysis by

102 splitting each consensus sequence using getfasta from the bedtools suite, based on the gff3
103 annotation file associated to the *B. pendula* reference assembly (Salojärvi et al. 2017). Columns
104 in the MSA with more than two masked sites were removed using trimAl v 1.4.1 (Capella-
105 Gutiérrez et al. 2009). Each MSA contains eight fixed birch species (*B. albosinensis*, *B. humilis*,
106 *B. lenta*, *B. nana*, *B. occidentalis*, *B. pendula*, *B. platyphylla*, and *B. populifolia*) and two alder
107 species (*A. glutinosa* and *A. incana*). Aside from *B. albosinensis* and *B. humilis*, WGS accessions
108 were always selected when generating the MSAs. Additionally, each MSA contains a nucleotide
109 sequence associated to one of the 269 *B. pubescens* samples included in this study, with each
110 *pubescens* specimen therefore being the subject of a separate phylogenetic analysis. In total,
111 431,207 (1,603 loci x 269 samples) MSAs were generated. We also prepared MSAs where the
112 *pubescens* nucleotide sequence was replaced by one of the 25 tetraploid *B. pendula* accessions
113 or one of the two triploid hybrids.

114

115 **Phylogenetic Analysis: Detailed Description**

116

117 Phylogenetic reconstruction of individual gene families was performed using maximum-
118 likelihood as implemented in IQ-TREE2 v 2.0-rc2-omp-mpi (Minh et al. 2020) with 1000
119 ultrafast bootstrap replicates (Hoang et al. 2018) and substitution model selection executed using
120 ModelFinder (Kalyaanamoorthy et al. 2017). MSAs were discarded and subsequently omitted
121 during downstream analysis if IQ-TREE2 failed to converge, or if the MSA contained less than
122 100 parsimony-informative sites, over 50% of gaps or other ambiguities, or contained two or
123 more identical nucleotide sequences.

124

125 Species trees were inferred using ASTRAL v 5.7.3 (Zhang et al. 2018), a super-tree
126 inference method statistically consistent under the multi-species coalescent model, based on the
127 phylogenies estimated previously for each individual gene family using IQ-TREE2. Options

128 used while running IQ-TREE2 and ASTRAL were identical to those described in a previous
129 paper (Leal et al. 2023).

130

131 Because phylogenetic inference was based on genomic data obtained using different
132 sequencing approaches (either WGS or exome capture), a preliminary phylogenetic analysis was
133 carried out for a special set of MSAs that included both WGS and TEC sequences for four birch
134 species: *B. nana*, *B. pendula*, *B. platyphylla*, and *B. pubescens*. This was done as a control in
135 order to ascertain whether the inclusion of libraries produced using disparate technologies is
136 likely to induce biases or artifacts during phylogenetic reconstruction. The inferred species tree
137 shows that WGS and TEC sequences associated to the same species always pair together, thus
138 suggesting that no major drawbacks can be inferred from mixing WGS and TEC sequences
139 during phylogenetic reconstruction (Supplementary Fig. S4). A similar tree topology was
140 obtained when the analysis was rerun for different North-Scandinavian *B. pubescens* TEC
141 sequences (data not shown).

142

143 Finally, there might also be some concerns about whether the use of exonic data, as
144 opposed to WGS, might induce any sort of artifact in the polyploid pairing profiles. While in the
145 current study we make use of exonic data, that is, a subset of all protein coding regions present
146 in the *B. pubescens* genome, selection of the genes included in the probe design was agnostic as
147 to their reticulated origin, as this information was not available at the time. Analysis of a single
148 *B. pubescens* individual originating from northern Finland and for which WGS data was
149 available (see Supplementary Materials 2) yielded pairing profiles similar to those observed for
150 the Finnish population (data not shown).

151

152

153

154 **Population Structure Analysis: Detailed Description**

155

156 Bayesian statistical inference of admixture levels between *B. pubescens* populations and
157 different birch species was performed with STRUCTURE v 2.3.4 (Pritchard et al. 2000), a
158 model-based method suitable for the analysis of mixed ploidy datasets (Dufresne et al. 2014,
159 Meirmans et al. 2018, Stift et al. 2019). As recommended by the authors, diploid samples were
160 coded as if tetraploid but with the two extra alleles flagged as missing data. Structure and
161 admixture inference were based on the analysis of 10,000 variant loci in 126 birch accessions.
162 Sixteen independent runs were performed for each K value (number of clusters), with K ranging
163 from 2 to 9. Parallelization was implemented using Structure_threader v. 1.3.10 (Pina-Martins
164 et al. 2017). For each run, the Monte Carlo Markov Chain was run for 250,000 iterations after a
165 burn-in period of 100,000 iterations. STRUCTURE was run using the following options:
166 'admixture model', 'correlated allele frequencies', and the 'LOCPRIOR model'. The latter allows
167 sampling location to assist in the clustering process and its use is recommended when assessing
168 the presence of structure among weakly divergent populations (Hubisz et al. 2009). Individual
169 values for α , the relative admixture parameter, were inferred for each population. When in the
170 presence of unbalanced sampling, allowing α values to vary across populations improves the
171 accuracy in the estimation of the optimal K value during downstream analysis, as long as the
172 number of clusters is not too large (< 20 ; Wang 2017). In order to further minimize the effect of
173 unbalanced population sizes, the number of *B. pubescens* samples of Scandinavian origin was
174 also downsampled. Finally, the λ value, the Dirichlet prior parameter used to model the
175 distribution of allele frequencies, was also optimized as the (fixed) default value is often not
176 appropriate for analyses using SNP data (Porrás-Hurtado et al. 2013). The most likely number
177 of ancestral populations was determined using both Evanno's ΔK statistic (Evanno et al. 2005)
178 and the $\ln \Pr(X|K)$ metric, the approximated likelihood of the data given K (Pritchard et al. 2000),

179 averaged across replicates. Output results for the 16 replicates were combined for each K using
180 StructureSelector (Li and Liu 2018) and Clumpp v. 1.1 (Jakobsson and Rosenberg 2007).

181

182 The presence of population genetic structure was also investigated using discriminant
183 analysis of principal components (DAPC; Jombart et al. 2010) with *adegenet* v 2.1.7, an R
184 package designed to perform multivariate analysis of genetic markers and which can handle
185 mixed-ploidy datasets (Jombart 2008; Dufresne et al. 2014; Meirmans et al. 2018). In order to
186 minimize within-cluster variance, DAPC first executes a data reduction step using principal
187 component analysis (PCA) and then performs a discriminant analysis on the retained principal
188 components (Jombart 2008). DAPC was performed on 50,000 variant loci belonging to 49 birch
189 accessions. In order to minimize bias on PCA projections due to uneven sampling (McVean
190 2009), two to five samples were selected for each species/ploidy/location. The optimal number
191 and membership of the clusters present in the dataset was determined using the 'find.clusters'
192 function in *adegenet*, which performs a k-means clustering on the PCA transformed data. Results
193 show that diploid and autotetraploid *B. pendula* samples cluster together (Fig. S11a), suggesting
194 that both originate from a single gene pool (Meirmans et al. 2018). Samples obtained through
195 WGS and TEC cluster together in all four species (*B. nana*, *B. pubescens*, *B. platyphylla* and *B.*
196 *pendula*) for which both types of samples were available (Fig. S11a). Together with the
197 phylogenetic tree obtained when both types of samples are included (Supplementary Fig. S4),
198 these results provide further evidence that mixing libraries obtained using different sequencing
199 approaches did not give rise to major biases or artifacts during downstream analyses.

200

201 Prior to running STRUCTURE and *adegenet*, private alleles were removed using the
202 VariantFiltration tool in the GATK suite. Sites in linkage disequilibrium (LD) were removed
203 using a modified version of scripts by Weitz and colleagues used to perform LD pruning in

204 polyploid species (Weitz et al. 2021). Only variant sites within intronic regions (putatively
205 neutral SNPs) and genotyped in all samples were included in the analysis.

206

207 **Coalescent Analysis: Detailed Description**

208

209 The approach used to determine the best evolutionary model using fastsimcoal2
210 (Excoffier et al. 2013), perform model optimization, and carry out final estimation of the
211 confidence intervals (CI), involved three separate steps (Arnold et al. 2016).

212

213 I) First we built simple demographic models for all possible phylogenetic relationships
214 between the three species included (3 models in total) and fitted them against the observed SFS
215 data using fastsimcoal2. Each model was fit to SNP data using 50 independent runs of
216 *fastsimcoal2*. At this stage, the only migration events allowed were the presence of gene flow
217 from *B. pendula* to *B. pubescens*. Comparison of model likelihoods, with the aim of determining
218 which model has the highest probability of being correct given the candidate set of models, was
219 performed using the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), as described in Johnson and Omland
220 (2004) and Arnold et al. (2016). In short, we started by computing the AIC value for model i ,
221 containing d_i parameters and maximum estimated likelihood MEL_i , using:

222

$$223 \quad AIC_i = 2d_i - 2\ln(MEL_i) \quad (S1)$$

224

225 These values are then used to estimate normalized Akaike weights (w) for each model using:

226

$$227 \quad w_i = \left[\frac{e^{-0.5A_i}}{\sum_k e^{-0.5A_k}} \right] \quad (S2)$$

228 with

229
$$\Delta_i = AIC_i - \min(\{AIC_1, \dots, AIC_N\}) \quad (S3)$$

230

231 Akaike weights can be interpreted as the probability that model i is the one that best fits the data
232 among the N models considered (Johnson and Omland 2004). Results are shown in
233 Supplementary Table S3.

234

235 II) The best evolutionary model determined above was then further optimized by
236 independently testing all possible migration combinations across species (129 models; 50
237 independent runs per model). As before, comparisons of model likelihoods using the AIC was
238 used to determine the best overall model. Results are shown in *Supplementary Materials 5*.

239

240 III) Following the guidelines suggested by the authors (fastsimcoal2 v. 2.7 manual,
241 <http://cmpg.unibe.ch/software/fastsimcoal2/man/fastsimcoal27.pdf>, last accessed 2023-05-09),
242 estimation of confidence intervals was performed using parametric bootstrap. This is done by
243 first simulating DNA sequences (and associated SFS) based on the parameters estimated for the
244 best, optimized model. This process is repeated multiple times to create 100 replicates, and then
245 50 independent fastsimcoal2 runs are performed for each replicate. Finally, confidence intervals
246 are computed based on the distributions obtained. Results are shown in Supplementary Table S4.

247

248 Next, examples of fastsimcoal2 input templates are provided for the model shown in Figure 5.
249 The mutation rate used was taken from Salojärvi et al. 2017.

250

```

251 fastsimcoal2 tpl input file:
252
253
254 //Number of population samples (demes)
255 3 samples to simulate :
256 //Population effective sizes (number of genes)
257 PUBpopsize
258 PENDpopsize
259 PLATYpopsize
260 //Sample sizes
261 16
262 16
263 16
264 //Growth rates      : negative growth implies population expansion
265 0
266 0
267 0
268 //Number of migration matrices : 0 implies no migration between demes
269 3
270 //Migration matrix 0
271 0.0000 MIG0_pubpen MIG0_pubpla
272 MIG0_penpub 0.0000 MIG0_penpla
273 MIG0_plapub MIG0_plapen 0.0000
274 //Migration matrix 1
275 0.0000 MIG1_pubpen 0.0000
276 MIG1_penpub 0.0000 0.0000
277 0.0000 0.0000 0.0000
278 //Migration matrix 2
279 0.0000 0.0000 0.0000
280 0.0000 0.0000 0.0000
281 0.0000 0.0000 0.0000
282 //historical event: time, source, sink, migrants, new size, new growth rate, migr. matrix
283 2 historical event
284 TDIV1 2 1 1 ResizeTime1 0 1
285 TDIV2 0 1 1 ResizeTime2 0 2
286 //Number of independent loci [chromosome]
287 1 0
288 //Per chromosome: Number of linkage blocks
289 1
290 //per Block: data type, num loci, rec. rate and mut rate + optional parameters
291 FREQ 1 0 9.5e-9 OUTEXP
292

```

293

```

294 fastsimcoal2 est input file:
295
296 // Priors and rules file
297 // *****
298
299 [PARAMETERS]
300 // #isInt? #name #dist.#min #max
301 // all N are in number of haploid individuals
302 1 PUBpopsize unif 1000 1e6 output
303 1 PENDpopsize unif 1000 1e6 output
304 1 PLATYpopsize unif 1000 1e6 output
305 1 ANCPopsize1 unif 1e4 5e6 output
306 1 ANCPopsize2 unif 1e4 5e6 output
307 1 TDIV1 unif 600 100000 output
308 1 TIMEextra unif 1 1000000 hide
309 0 MIG0_pubpen logunif 1e-7 1e-4 output
310 0 MIG0_pubpla logunif 1e-7 1e-4 output
311 0 MIG0_penpub logunif 0 0 output
312 0 MIG0_penpla logunif 1e-7 1e-4 output
313 0 MIG0_plapen logunif 1e-7 1e-4 output
314 0 MIG0_plapub logunif 1e-7 1e-4 output
315 0 MIG1_pubpen logunif 0 0 output
316 0 MIG1_penpub logunif 0 0 output
317
318 [COMPLEX PARAMETERS]
319 1 TDIV2 = TDIV1+TIMEextra output
320 0 ResizeTime1 = ANCPopsize1/PENDpopsize hide
321 0 ResizeTime2 = ANCPopsize2/ANCPopsize1 hide
322 0 Nm_pubpen0 = MIG0_pubpen*PUBpopsize output
323 0 Nm_pubpla0 = MIG0_pubpla*PUBpopsize output
324 0 Nm_penpub0 = MIG0_penpub*PENDpopsize output
325 0 Nm_penpla0 = MIG0_penpla*PENDpopsize output
326 0 Nm_plapen0 = MIG0_plapen*PLAYTpopsize output
327 0 Nm_plapub0 = MIG0_plapub*PLAYTpopsize output
328 0 Nm_pubpen1 = MIG1_pubpen*PUBpopsize output
329 0 Nm_penpub1 = MIG1_penpub*PENDpopsize output
330
331

```

332 **Geographic Distribution and Functional Analysis of Alleles of *B. nana* and *B. humilis***

333 **Ancestry: Detailed Description**

334

335 K-means cluster analysis

336 K-means cluster analysis was used to partition *B. pubescens* loci containing alleles of *B. nana* or

337 *B. humilis* ancestry in groups with a similar abundance profile across geographic locations.

338 Clustering analysis was performed using the kmeans algorithm as implemented in MATLAB, v.

339 2019a (Mathworks), using correlation as the distance metric. The analysis was executed 50 times

340 for each k , with different random initializations, and the within cluster dissimilarity value (W_K ,

341 the total sum of distances to the cluster centroids) was computed at each iteration and for each

342 k . The optimal number of clusters, k^* , was inferred by determining the k at which the change in

343 the cluster dissimilarity value across consecutive k -values ($W_K - W_{K+1}$) levels off (Hastie et al.

344 2009).

345

346 Functional annotation

347 Functional annotation of individual *B. pubescens*/*B. pendula* genes of interest was based on the

348 annotation of homologous genes in the *Arabidopsis thaliana* model species, and relied on the

349 association file between *A. thaliana* and *B. pendula* genes released with the *B. pendula* reference

350 assembly (Salojärvi et al. 2017). Because we make use of exome data, that is, a non-random set

351 of genomic markers that includes a large number of genes pre-selected based on their very

352 functional role, we opted against performing a formal gene ontology enrichment analysis, as the

353 latter would be likely to be biased towards biological functions overrepresented in the probe

354 design.

355

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518 Table S1 | **Sample information (*Betula* and *Alnus*)**. Specie's name, number of individuals
 519 sequenced, sequencing technology, ploidy, number of chromosomes found in somatic cells, and
 520 geographic distribution. *Betula* genus's base chromosome number is $x=14$. See *Supplementary*
 521 *Materials 2* for ENA accession number for each sample.

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Genus	Species	Number of individuals	Sequencing	Ploidy	Chromosome No.	Distribution	Source ^a
<i>Betula</i>	<i>B. albosinensis</i> Burk.	1	exome capture	tetraploid	2n=4x=56 ^b	Asia	BBG
	<i>B. humilis</i> Schrk.	2	exome capture	diploid	2n=2x=28	Asia, Europe	NP
	<i>B. lenta</i> L.	1	WGS	diploid	2n=2x=28	North America	HBG (JS)
	<i>B. nana</i> L.	1	WGS	diploid	2n=2x=28	Asia, Europe, N. America	FFR (JS)
		3	exome capture	diploid	2n=2x=28	Asia, Europe, N. America	NP
	<i>B. occidentalis</i> Hook	1	WGS	diploid	2n=2x=28	North America	HBG (JS)
	<i>B. pendula</i> Roth.	2	WGS	diploid	2n=2x=28	Asia, Europe	NP (JS)
		20	exome capture	diploid	2n=2x=28	Asia, Europe	NP (PM)
	<i>B. pendula</i> (4X)	25	exome capture	tetraploid	2n=4x=56		NP (PM)
	<i>B. pendula</i> (3X)	1	exome capture	triploid	2n=3x=42		NP (PM)
	<i>B. platyphylla</i> Suk.	1	WGS	diploid	2n=2x=28	Asia	HBG (JS)
		15	exome capture	diploid	2n=2x=28	Asia	NP
	<i>B. populifolia</i> Marsh.	1	WGS	diploid	2n=2x=28	North America	HBG (JS)
	<i>B. pubescens</i> Ehrh.	1	WGS	tetraploid	2n=4x=56	Asia, Europe	HBG (JS)
	269	exome capture	tetraploid	2n=4x=56	Asia, Europe	NP	
	<i>B. pendula</i> x <i>B. pubescens</i>	1	exome capture	triploid	2n=3x=42		NP
<i>Alnus</i> (outgroup)	<i>A. glutinosa</i>	1	WGS				NP (JS)
	<i>A. incana</i>	1	WGS				NP (JS)

^a BBG = Bergius Botanic Garden (Sweden); FFR = The Finnish Research Institute (Finland); HBG = Helsinki Botanical Gardens (Finland); JS = Salojärvi et al. (2017); NP = natural population in Europe; PM = Milesi et al. (2023)

^b Both diploid and tetraploid specimens have been documented (Hu et al. 2019)

533 Table S2 | **Optimized genomic composition in the presence of homoeologous replacement** –
534 *B. pubescens* genomic composition as predicted by each evolutionary model, in the absence (**a**)
535 or presence (**b**) of homoeologous replacement. P, N, H, P_y, and A indicate the hypothetical
536 evolutionary origin of each subgenomic component in the tetraploid (*B. pendula*, *B. nana*, *B.*
537 *humilis*, *B. platyphylla*, and common ancestor of *B. pendula* and *B. platyphylla*, respectively).
538 Modeling data summarizes optimized results [top 5% simulation runs (50 out of 1000 runs)]
539 obtained using approximate Bayesian computation having as a reference the values observed
540 experimentally for a population in Southern Sweden. "1+ copies": percentage of loci with at least
541 one gene copy originating from, respectively, *B. nana*, *B. humilis*, *B. pendula*, or the common
542 ancestor of *B. pendula* and *B. platyphylla*. "4 copies": percentage of loci where all four gene
543 copies originate from one of the subgenomes via homoeologous replacement. Weighted *L2* norm
544 distance, averaged over the top 5% simulation run, is also shown for each model. Values for
545 AAAA model (best model in the absence of homoeologous replacement) are highlighted in green.
546 Total levels of homoeologous replacement are highlighted in lilac (includes only values for gene
547 copies originating from *B. pendula* or from the ancestor of *B. pendula* and *B. platyphylla*).
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No Homoeologous Replacement								
MODEL	L2 norm	1+ copies				All 4 copies		
		nana	humilis	pendula	ancestral	pendula	ancestral	Total
1 PPPP	0.74 ± 0.01	0.42 ± 0.03	0.36 ± 0.02	0.97 ± 0.01	-	0.35 ± 0.03	-	0.35
2 AAAA	0.49 ± 0.01	0.41 ± 0.03	0.34 ± 0.02	0.79 ± 0.02	0.82 ± 0.02	0.13 ± 0.02	0.17 ± 0.02	0.30
3 PPNN	1.58 ± 0.01	0.53 ± 0.02	0.50 ± 0.03	0.98 ± 0.01	-	-	-	-
4 PPHH	1.58 ± 0.01	0.56 ± 0.03	0.48 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.01	-	-	-	-
5 PPPyPy	1.07 ± 0.02	0.49 ± 0.04	0.40 ± 0.03	0.95 ± 0.01	-	-	-	-
6 PPNH	1.59 ± 0.01	0.60 ± 0.03	0.48 ± 0.02	0.91 ± 0.03	-	-	-	-
7 AANN	1.50 ± 0.01	0.53 ± 0.02	0.51 ± 0.02	0.88 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.01	-	-	-
8 AAHH	1.55 ± 0.01	0.55 ± 0.03	0.48 ± 0.02	0.81 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.01	-	-	-
9 AANH	1.58 ± 0.01	0.50 ± 0.03	0.54 ± 0.02	0.81 ± 0.02	0.89 ± 0.01	-	-	-

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With Homoeologous Replacement (allopolyploid models only)											
MODEL	L2 norm	1+ copies				All 4 copies (homoeologous replacement)					
		nana	humilis	pendula	ancestral	nana	humilis	platyphylla	pendula	ancestral	Total
1 PPPP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2 AAAA	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3 PPNN	0.76 ± 0.02	0.41 ± 0.04	0.35 ± 0.02	0.95 ± 0.02	-	0.01 ± 0.01	-	-	0.37 ± 0.02	-	0.37
4 PPHH	0.76 ± 0.02	0.58 ± 0.05	0.38 ± 0.02	0.97 ± 0.01	-	-	0.01 ± 0.01	-	0.34 ± 0.05	-	0.34
5 PPPyPy	0.66 ± 0.02	0.40 ± 0.03	0.33 ± 0.02	0.92 ± 0.03	-	-	-	0.02 ± 0.01	0.29 ± 0.02	-	0.29
6 PPNH	0.75 ± 0.02	0.35 ± 0.04	0.31 ± 0.03	0.94 ± 0.05	-	0.01 ± 0.01	0.03 ± 0.01	-	0.39 ± 0.03	-	0.39
7 AANN	0.55 ± 0.02	0.35 ± 0.03	0.36 ± 0.02	0.80 ± 0.02	0.80 ± 0.02	0.02 ± 0.01	-	-	0.17 ± 0.02	0.17 ± 0.02	0.34
8 AAHH	0.53 ± 0.02	0.39 ± 0.04	0.31 ± 0.03	0.77 ± 0.02	0.78 ± 0.03	-	0.02 ± 0.01	-	0.18 ± 0.02	0.18 ± 0.02	0.36
9 AANH	0.57 ± 0.02	0.41 ± 0.04	0.34 ± 0.03	0.74 ± 0.03	0.76 ± 0.03	0.01 ± 0.01	0.02 ± 0.01	-	0.17 ± 0.02	0.18 ± 0.02	0.35

573 Table S3 | **Likelihood analysis of possible phylogenies.** Likelihood (*Lhood*) analysis for
574 different phylogenetic topologies and *B. pubescens* populations estimated using *fastsimcoal2*.
575 Each model was fit to SNP data using 50 runs of *fastsimcoal2*. Possibility of gene flow from *B.*
576 *pendula* to *B. pubescens* is included in all models. Akaike information criteria (AIC), AIC
577 variation versus best model (Δ), and Akaike weights (**w**) also shown. AIC analysis is performed
578 independently for each *B. pubescens* population. Akaike weights show probability that model *i*
579 is the best model for the observed data, given the candidate set of models.

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Population	Phylogeny (model)	Max $\log_{10}(\text{Lhood}_i)$	AIC_i	Δ_i	w_i	Notes
Central Europe	((PEN, PUB), PLA)	-28527.1	65702.07521	698.6043172	1.9953E-152	best model
	((PEN, PLA), PUB)	-28223.7	65003.47089	0	1	
	(PEN, (PUB, PLA))	-28435.7	65491.61893	488.1480397	1.0000E-106	
Southern Sweden	((PEN, PUB), PLA)	-31814.8	73272.28422	351.8350022	3.98107E-77	best model
	((PEN, PLA), PUB)	-31662	72920.44921	0	1	
	(PEN, (PUB, PLA))	-31810.8	73263.07388	342.6246618	3.98107E-75	
Central Asia	((PEN, PUB), PLA)	-34656.7	79816.00079	705.281814	7.0795E-154	best model
	((PEN, PLA), PUB)	-34350.4	79110.71898	0	1	
	(PEN, (PUB, PLA))	-34670.7	79848.23698	737.5180053	7.0795E-161	
Spain	((PEN, PUB), PLA)	-49845	114788.354	372.7885266	1.12202E-81	best model
	((PEN, PLA), PUB)	-49683.1	114415.5654	0	1	
	(PEN, (PUB, PLA))	-49867	114839.0108	423.4453986	1.12202E-92	

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591 Table S4 | **Maximum likelihood estimates (MLE) for parameters associated to evolutionary**
592 **model with highest Akaike weight.** Parameters estimated using *fastsimcoal2* for the ((*B.*
593 *pendula*, *B. platyphylla*), *B. pubescens*) phylogenetic topology, with the *B. pubescens* population
594 containing individuals sampled from Central Europe. Upper and lower confidence intervals
595 (95%) were estimated using parametric bootstrap based on 100 replicates, and then performing
596 inference on each replicate based on 50 runs with *fastsimcoal2*. Population sizes are $2N_e$ or $4N_e$
597 haploid numbers for diploid and tetraploid species, respectively. Divergence times are shown in
598 number of generations. The mean number of individuals in the sink population that migrated
599 from the source population each generation was computed by multiplying the population size by
600 the migration probability. Only *B. pubescens* loci containing four gene copies of *B. pendula/B.*
601 *platyphylla* ancestry were included in the analysis (loci containing one or more gene copies
602 originating from *B. nana* or *B. humilis* were excluded).

	MLEs	Lower 95% CI	Upper 95% CI	Notes	
603	PUBpopsize	628,719	614,818	642,620	<i>B. pubescens</i> population size ($4N_e$)
604	PENDpopsize	178,164	174,431	181,896	<i>B. pendula</i> population size ($2N_e$)
	PLATYpopsize	95,847	93,734	97,959	<i>B. platyphylla</i> population size ($2N_e$)
605	ANCpopsize1	381,235	356,410	406,061	Ancestral population size of common ancestor of <i>B. pendula</i> and <i>B. platyphylla</i>
	ANCpopsize2	132,634	129,624	135,645	Ancestral population size of common ancestor of all three species
	TDIV1	100,120	97,821	102,419	<i>B. pendula</i> / <i>B. platyphylla</i> divergence time
606	TDIV2	183,594	178,659	188,529	Divergence time between <i>B. pubescens</i> and common ancestor of <i>B. pendula</i> and <i>B. platyphylla</i>
	MIG0_pubpen	1.16E-05	1.13E-05	1.19E-05	Backwards migration probability from <i>B. pubescens</i> to <i>B. pendula</i>
607	MIG0_pubpla	7.72E-07	7.08E-07	8.36E-07	Backwards migration probability from <i>B. pubescens</i> to <i>B. platyphylla</i>
	MIG0_penpub	set to zero			Backwards migration probability from <i>B. pendula</i> to <i>B. pubescens</i>
	MIG0_penpla	1.24E-06	1.12E-06	1.35E-06	Backwards migration probability from <i>B. pendula</i> to <i>B. platyphylla</i>
608	MIG0_plapen	3.38E-06	3.07E-06	3.68E-06	Backwards migration probability from <i>B. platyphylla</i> to <i>B. pendula</i>
	MIG0_plapub	5.90E-06	5.44E-06	6.36E-06	Backwards migration probability from <i>B. platyphylla</i> to <i>B. pubescens</i>
	MIG1_pubpen	set to zero			Backwards migration probability from <i>B. pubescens</i> to common ancestor of <i>B. pendula/B. platyphylla</i>
609	MIG1_penpub	set to zero			Backwards migration probability from common ancestor of <i>B. pendula/B. platyphylla</i> to <i>B. pubescens</i>
	Nm_pubpen0	6.40079	6.16533	6.63625	MIG0_pubpen * PUBpopsize
610	Nm_pubpla0	0.420072	0.387006	0.453139	MIG0_pubpla * PUBpopsize
	Nm_penpub0	set to zero			MIG0_penpub * PENDpopsize
	Nm_penpla0	0.185597	0.169749	0.201445	MIG0_penpla * PENDpopsize
611	Nm_plapen0	0.206294	0.190474	0.222115	MIG0_plapen * PLATYpopsize
	Nm_plapub0	0.345092	0.32922	0.360963	MIG0_plapub * PLATYpopsize
612	Nm_pubpen1	set to zero			MIG1_pubpen * PUBpopsize
	Nm_penpub1	set to zero			MIG1_penpub * ANCPopsize1

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614 Table S5 | *B. pubescens* loci containing exclusively alleles inherited from *B. pendula* or from
 615 the common ancestor of *B. pendula* and *B. platyphylla*.

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Locus	<i>A. thaliana</i> homolog	Function
Loci containing exclusively alleles inherited from the common ancestor of <i>B. pendula</i> and <i>B. platyphylla</i>		
Bpev01.c0752.g0012	TOC159 Translocase of chloroplast 159	Required for chloroplast biogenesis (Bauer et al. 2000)
Loci containing exclusively alleles inherited from <i>B. pendula</i>		
Bpev01.c0223.g0009	At2g37230 Pentatricopeptide repeat-containing protein	chloroplast protein
Bpev01.c0017.g0022	At1g15240	uncharacterized protein

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629 Figure S1 | *B. pubescens* sampling locations – Sampling locations (●) and *B. pubescens* natural
 630 distribution range. Species range adapted from Caudullo et al. (2017), Atkinson (1992), and
 631 Ashburner and McAllister (2013).

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| 1 Spain | 6 Sweden (Djurrod) | 19 Norway (Kautokeino) |
| 2 Poland | 7 Sweden (Skatelov) | 20 Norway (Skadi) |
| 3 Ukraine | 8 Sweden (Vallerstad) | 21 Finland |
| 4 Lithuania | 9 Sweden (Aspo) | 22 Russia (Urals) |
| 5 Norway (south) | 10 Sweden (Moklinta) | 23 Russia (Nazyvayevsky) |
| | 11 Sweden (Lingbo) | |
| | 12 Sweden (Gnarp) | |
| | 13 Sweden (Docksta) | |
| | 14 Sweden (Brattby) | |
| | 15 Sweden (Burea) | |
| | 16 Sweden (Pitea) | |
| | 17 Sweden (Jokkmokk) | |
| | 18 Sweden (Nedre Soppero) | |

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649 Figure S2 | **Classification of birch specimens** – Read frequency distributions for biallelic
 650 variants (left-most column) and pairing patterns for focal species (two right-most columns) for
 651 five birch samples: **(a)** *B. pubescens*; **(b)** diploid *B. pendula*; **(c)** autotetraploid *B. pendula*; **(d)**
 652 triploid *B. pendula*; and **(e)** *B. pendula* x *B. pubescens* triploid hybrid. **Barplots** on the right side
 653 show frequency with which the focal birch specimen pairs with other species and is based on
 654 phylogenetic analysis of individual gene families using IQ-TREE2. Identity of the reference
 655 sequence used during genomic polarization of focal birch species shown atop each of the two
 656 right-most columns.

675 Figure S3 | **Bioinformatics pipeline** – Synoptic diagram displaying pipeline developed to
 676 produced observed pairing profiles per population and polarizing geometry (left panel) and
 677 perform polyploidization model optimization (right panel). Polarization geometry refers to
 678 reference sequence used during polarization (one of *B. pendula*, *B. platyphylla*, *B. nana*, or *B.*
 679 *humilis*). During polyploidization model optimization, comparison between simulated and
 680 observed pairing profiles (using the L2 norm distance) is used to find the best model parameters
 681 and estimate introgression levels. Initial model optimization is performed using simulated
 682 annealing. Final model optimization performed using an approximate Bayesian computation
 683 (ABC) rejection algorithm with priors sampled from distribution centered on model parameters
 684 estimated using simulated annealing. Optimization was done separately for each
 685 polyploidization model and *B. pubescens* population. Nine different polyploidization models
 686 were tested: PPPP, AAAA, PPNN, PPHH, PPP_yP_y, PPNH, AANN, AAHH, and AANH. *B.*
 687 *pubescens* populations modeled: Arctic, Northern Sweden, Southern Sweden, Central Asia,
 688 Lithuania, Ukraine, and Southwestern Europe.

701 **Figure S4 | Birch phylogeny based on WGS and TEC sequences** – Species tree cladogram for
 702 11 Betulaceae species. Four birch species (*B. nana*, *B. pendula*, *B. platyphylla*, and *B. pubescens*)
 703 are represented by both whole genome sequencing (WGS) and targeted exome capture (TEC)
 704 accessions. WGS and TEC sequences pair together in all four cases. Phylogenies obtained using
 705 ASTRAL based on 490 gene families (exonic sequences only). Pie charts show quartet support
 706 for each branch. Precise support values are shown for the four focal clades. Both *B. pubescens*
 707 specimens are from northern Finland (see *Supplementary Materials 2*). *B. pubescens* sequences
 708 were polarized using *B. humilis* as the reference sequence (●). Only the *B. pubescens* sequences
 709 are polarized. Sample ID provided after species name.

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721 Figure S5 | **SYMPHY input phylogeny used in the simulation of the birch genus.** Example
722 of input tree, mimicking the *Betulaceae* phylogeny, used for testing different evolutionary
723 models for *B. pubescens*, based on different parental species (●) and levels of introgressive
724 hybridization between *B. pubescens* and a third species (○). Phylogenetic position of parental
725 species and hybridizing species vary according to the model. *Note:* SIMPHY requires starting
726 trees to be ultrametric, that is, the distance from the root must be the same for every tree tip.

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742 Figure S6 | ***B. pubescens* evolutionary models** – Schematic representation of the nine
743 polyploidization models considered. For each model, different levels of hybridization with one
744 or more third species are hypothesized. Each H_i value represents a fraction of the genome with
745 a specific evolutionary history. For example, parameter H_2 in Model 1 represents the fraction of
746 the *B. pubescens* genome that contains alleles of both *B. humilis* and *B. pendula* origin, with the
747 *humilis* alleles having been acquired via introgression. Simulated annealing and approximate
748 Bayesian computation are used to optimize the H_i values for each model and sampling location.
749 Two extra parameters (not shown in the diagram below) are used to model genus-wide ILS levels,
750 and specific ILS levels between *B. pendula* and *B. platyphylla*. P , N , H , P_y and A indicate the
751 hypothetical evolutionary origin of each subgenomic component in the tetraploid (*B. pendula*,
752 *B. nana*, *B. humilis*, *B. platyphylla*, and the common ancestor of *B. pendula*/*B. platyphylla*,
753 respectively). **Insert:** Notice that while the polarization protocol is sensitive to the evolutionary
754 origin of each locus in the polyploid, in general it cannot be used to estimate allele dosage (copy
755 number of each allele).
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Model 7

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Model 8

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HH

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Model 9

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797 Figure S7 | ***B. pubescens* polyploid-pairing frequencies** – Barplots show the frequency
 798 with which *B. pubescens* pairs with other birch species, for different populations and
 799 polarization settings, based on phylogenetic analysis of individual gene families using IQ-
 800 TREE2. Population numbers correspond to locations shown in Supplementary Fig. S1. The
 801 number of specimens per population (N) is also provided. In the x-axis, 'basal' indicates
 802 instances when the polyploid is an outgroup to all birch species included in the analysis, 'pend-
 803 platy' indicates that the polyploid is an outgroup to the *pendula-platyphylla* clade, 'pop_out'
 804 indicates that the polyploid is an outgroup to the *pendula-platyphylla-populifolia* clade, and so
 805 on.

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Reference sequence during polarization

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844 Figure S8 | **4X *B. pendula* polyploid-pairing frequencies** – Barplots show the frequency with
 845 which the autotetraploid *B. pendula* pairs with other birch species, for different polarization
 846 settings, and is based on phylogenetic analysis of individual gene families using IQ-TREE2.

855 **Figure S9 | STRUCTURE profiles for representative *Betula* populations** – Estimated genetic
856 admixture of 126 *Betula* samples according to the STRUCTURE analysis based on 10,000
857 variant loci, for K=2 to K= 9. Each individual is represented by a vertical column. Data for
858 diploid (2X) and tetraploid samples (4X) shown separately to facilitate interpretation. Data for
859 tetraploid samples is sorted by latitude from left (south) to right (north). Population location and
860 identifiers (based on Figure S1): ES (1. Spain), PL (2. Poland), UA (3. Ukraine), CA-west (22.
861 Urals, Russia), LT (4. Lithuania), CA-east (23. Nazyvayevsky, Russia), SV-south (7. Skatelov,
862 Sweden), NO (5. southern Norway), FI (21. northern Finland), Arctic (20. Skadi, Norway).

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890 Figure S10 | **Clustering analysis based on STRUCTURE results** – Number of clusters
891 determined using the **(a)** Evvanno method (Evanno et al. 2005) and **(b)** the $\ln \Pr(X|K)$ statistic
892 (Pritchard et al. 2000) averaged across replicates.

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913 Figure S11 | **DAPC clustering analysis** – **(a)** DAPC plot for 49 birch accessions based on 50,000
914 variant loci. Four birch species (*B. nana*, *B. pendula*, *B. platyphylla* and *B. pubescens*) are
915 represented by both whole genome sequencing (WGS) and targeted exome capture (TEC)
916 accessions. *B. pendula* is represented by both diploid (2X) and tetraploid (4X) specimens. TEC
917 accessions: each species/ploidy/population is represented by 5 samples, apart from *B. humilis* (2)
918 and *B. nana* (3). WGS accessions: each species is represented by one sample, apart from *B.*
919 *pendula* which is represented by 2 samples. *B. pubescens* population location and identifiers
920 (based on Figure S1): Southwestern Europe (1.Spain), Central Europe (2.Poland, 3.Ukraine, and
921 4.Lithuania), Central Scandinavia (17-Jokkmokk-Sweden), Arctic (20.Skadi-Norway), Central
922 Asia (22-23.Russia). **(b)** Results from k-means clustering analysis of PCA transformed data,
923 based on same dataset described above and obtained using the 'find.clusters' function in *adeigenet*,
924 confirmed the presence of five clusters, with cluster membership being organized along species
925 lines. Red dashed line indicates optimal number of clusters based on the Bayesian Information
926 Criterion (BIC).
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951 Figure S12 | **Comparison of *B. pubescens* evolutionary models** – This is an extended version
 952 of Figure 3 that shows pairing frequencies for all nine models and also for multi-species clades.
 953 In the x-axis, 'basal' indicates instances when the polyploid is an outgroup to all birch species
 954 included in the analysis, 'pend-platy' indicates that the polyploid is an outgroup to the *pendula-*
 955 *platyphylla* clade, 'pop_out' indicates that the polyploid is an outgroup to the *pendula-*
 956 *platyphylla-populifolia* clade, and so on.

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Reference sequence during polarization

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Reference sequence during polarization

1026 Figure S13 | **AAAA autoploid model predictions** – Barplots show the frequency with
1027 which the polarized *B. pubescens* sequence pairs with other birch species, as predicted by the
1028 AAAA evolutionary model and for different polarization settings, based on phylogenetic
1029 analysis of individual gene families using IQ-TREE2. "AA" indicates the hypothetical
1030 evolutionary origin of each subgenomic component in the tetraploid (common ancestor of *B.*
1031 *pendula* and *B. platyphylla*). Modeling data summarizes optimized results [top 5% simulation
1032 runs (50 out of 1000 runs)], obtained using approximate Bayesian computation having as a
1033 reference the values observed experimentally (shown on top panel for each population). Each
1034 simulation run averages results over 25 independent replicates. Cyan bars indicate level of
1035 polyploid-pairing for the three key birch species. Bars in red indicate discrepancies between
1036 predicted and experimental results higher than 5 percentage points. The weighted L_2 norm
1037 distance, averaged over the top 5% simulation runs, measures the goodness of fit and includes
1038 data for all four polarizations (lower L_2 values denote a better fit). *pend_platy* indicates instances
1039 when the polarized polyploid sequence is an outgroup to the *pendula-platyphylla* clade.

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